

The Tyranny of Arm-Wrestling Methyls on Iron(II) Spin State in Pseudo-Octahedral [Fe(didentate)₃] Complexes.

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Supporting Information

(22 pages)

Table S1. Elemental Analysis of the primary $[\text{Fe}(\text{L5})_3](\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes.

Molecular formula, Mw /g·mol ⁻¹	Elemental analysis
$[\text{Fe}(\text{L5})_3](\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	calcd. %C 46.69 %H 3.71 %N 15.94
MM = 1053.9 g/mol	found %C 47.03 %H 3.52 %N 15.58
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$	calcd. %C 50.70 %H 4.41 %N 18.98
MM = 993.6 g/mol	found %C 50.59 %H 4.26 %N 19.13
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	calcd. %C 47.66 %H 4.50 %N 17.10
MM = 983.8 g/mol	found %C 47.22 %H 4.02 %N 17.53

Table S2 Crystal data and structure refinement for **L5**.

CCDC number	1988655
Empirical formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄
Formula weight	224.27
Temperature	180 K
Wavelength	1.54184 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>
Unit cell dimensions	<i>a</i> = 19.8873(10) Å
	<i>b</i> = 3.90974(16) Å
	<i>c</i> = 14.8924(7) Å
	α = 90°
	β = 107.876(5)°
	γ = 90°
Volume	1102.04(9) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	4
Density (calculated)	1.352 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.678 mm ⁻¹
<i>F</i> (000)	472
Crystal size	0.27 x 0.107 x 0.071 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	2.334 to 69.013°
Index ranges	-23 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 23, -4 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 4, -8 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17
Reflections collected	3876
Independent reflections	2010 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0146]
Completeness to theta = 67.500°	99.50%
Absorption correction	Analytical
Max. and min. transmission	0.955 and 0.872
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data / restraints / parameters	2010 / 0 / 156
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.086
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0385, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.0987
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0424, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1010
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.209 and -0.186 e.Å ⁻³

Table S3 Crystal data and structure refinement for [Fe(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (I) and [Ni(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (II).

	I	II
CCDC numbers	1988657	1988659
Empirical formula	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ Cl ₂ FeN ₁₂ O ₈	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ Cl ₂ NiN ₁₂ O ₈
Formula Unit	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ Cl ₂ FeN ₁₂ O ₈	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ Cl ₂ NiN ₁₂ O ₈
Formula weight	927.55	930.41
Temperature	180 K	180 K
Wavelength	1.54184 Å	1.54184 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>
	<i>a</i> = 8.2485(3) Å	<i>a</i> = 8.27280(10) Å
	<i>b</i> = 38.5553(14) Å	<i>b</i> = 38.2659(6) Å
Unit cell dimensions	<i>c</i> = 13.0716(5) Å	<i>c</i> = 12.9930(2) Å
	α = 90°	α = 90°
	β = 104.291(4)°	β = 104.434(2)°
	γ = 90°	γ = 90°
Volume	4028.5(3) Å ³	3983.31(11) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	4	4
Density (calculated)	1.529 Mg/m ³	1.551 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	4.818 mm ⁻¹	2.538 mm ⁻¹
<i>F</i> (000)	1912	1920
Crystal size	0.245 x 0.173 x 0.047 mm ³	0.273 x 0.132 x 0.056 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	2.292 to 68.768°	2.309 to 70.759°
Index ranges	-8 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 9, -45 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 46, -15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 15	-9 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 7, -46 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 32, -15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 15
Reflections collected	17901	16391
Independent reflections	7364 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0243]	7483 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0382]
Completeness to theta	(67.684°) 99.8%	(67.684°) 99.7%
Absorption correction	Analytical	Gaussian
Max. and min. transmission	0.801 and 0.489	1.000 and 0.732
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data / restraints / parameters	7364 / 158 / 582	7483 / 0 / 565
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.032	1.094
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0390, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.0934	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0563, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1408
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0435, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.0964	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0657, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1451
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.466 and -0.371 e.Å ⁻³	0.600 and -0.830 e.Å ⁻³

Table S4 Crystal data and structure refinement for $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**III**) and $[\text{Zn}(\text{L5})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**IV**).

	III	IV
CCDC number	1988656	1988657
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{78}\text{H}_{76}\text{B}_4\text{F}_{16}\text{N}_{24}\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{36}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{Zn}$
Formula Unit	$\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{36}\text{B}_2\text{F}_8\text{N}_{12}\text{Ni} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{36}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{Zn}$
Formula weight	1846.28	937.07
Temperature	180 K	180 K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	1.54184 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$	$P2_1/c$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 23.0916(4)$ Å	$a = 8.2559(3)$ Å
	$b = 23.1612(5)$ Å	$b = 38.5861(9)$ Å
	$c = 15.8218(2)$ Å	$c = 13.0163(3)$ Å
	$\alpha = 90^\circ$	$\alpha = 90^\circ$
	$\beta = 99.1601(14)^\circ$	$\beta = 104.250(3)^\circ$
	$\gamma = 90^\circ$	$\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	$8354.0(3)$ Å ³	$4018.9(2)$ Å ³
<i>Z</i>	4	4
Density (calculated)	1.468 Mg/m ³	1.549 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.549 mm ⁻¹	2.668 mm ⁻¹
<i>F</i> (000)	3792	1928
Crystal size	0.44 x 0.32 x 0.238 mm ³	0.192 x 0.09 x 0.028 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	1.787 to 28.156°	2.290 to 68.857°
Index ranges	$-25 \leq h \leq 30$, $-30 \leq k \leq 28$, $-20 \leq l \leq 20$	$-9 \leq h \leq 9$, $-30 \leq k \leq 46$, $-15 \leq l \leq 10$
Reflections collected	42210	17094
Independent reflections	17452 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0306]	7341 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0261]
Completeness to theta	(25.242°) 99.7%	(67.684°) 99.7%
Absorption correction	Gaussian	Gaussian
Max. and min. transmission	1.000 and 0.344	1.000 and 0.728
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data / restraints / parameters	17452 / 225 / 1187	7341 / 124 / 611
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.034	1.019
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0476, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1151	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0348, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.0847
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0668, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1287	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0475, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.0918
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.789 and -0.541 e.Å ⁻³	0.444 and -0.351 e.Å ⁻³

Figure S1 ORTEP view of the ligand **L5** (ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability) with numbering scheme.

Table S5: Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for ligand **L5**.

Bond distances (Å)			
N(1)-C(1)	1.3862(17)	C(1)-C(6)	1.4012(19)
N(1)-C(7)	1.3163(18)	C(2)-C(3)	1.381(2)
N(2)-C(6)	1.3775(17)	C(3)-C(4)	1.399(2)
N(2)-C(7)	1.3755(17)	C(4)-C(5)	1.379(2)
N(2)-C(8)	1.4518(17)	C(5)-C(6)	1.3914(19)
N(3)-C(9)	1.3397(19)	C(7)-C(9)	1.4769(18)
N(3)-C(10)	1.3326(19)	C(9)-C(12)	1.403(2)
N(4)-C(11)	1.333(2)	C(10)-C(11)	1.377(2)
N(4)-C(12)	1.3409(19)	C(12)-C(13)	1.496(2)
C(1)-C(2)	1.3940(19)		

Bond angles (°)			
C(7)-N(1)-C(1)	104.67(11)	N(2)-C(6)-C(5)	131.55(13)
C(6)-N(2)-C(8)	124.58(11)	C(5)-C(6)-C(1)	122.77(12)
C(7)-N(2)-C(6)	106.18(11)	N(1)-C(7)-N(2)	113.37(11)
C(7)-N(2)-C(8)	129.16(11)	N(1)-C(7)-C(9)	124.45(12)
C(10)-N(3)-C(9)	116.95(13)	N(2)-C(7)-C(9)	121.87(12)
C(11)-N(4)-C(12)	117.56(13)	N(3)-C(9)-C(7)	114.84(12)
N(1)-C(1)-C(2)	130.00(13)	N(3)-C(9)-C(12)	122.19(13)
N(1)-C(1)-C(6)	110.10(11)	C(12)-C(9)-C(7)	122.94(13)
C(2)-C(1)-C(6)	119.89(12)	N(3)-C(10)-C(11)	121.20(15)
C(3)-C(2)-C(1)	117.59(13)	N(4)-C(11)-C(10)	122.42(14)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	121.73(13)	N(4)-C(12)-C(9)	119.69(14)
C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	121.68(13)	N(4)-C(12)-C(13)	117.37(13)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	116.34(13)	C(9)-C(12)-C(13)	122.94(13)
N(2)-C(6)-C(1)	105.67(11)		

Table S6: Selected least-squares planes data for Ligand **L5**

Least Squares Planes Description	Mean Deviation (Å)	Max. Deviation (Å) and atom	Dihedral Angle (°)
Pyrazine 1 C9 N3 C10 C11 N4 C12	0.002	0.03 (N3)	35.2
Benzimidazole 1 C7 N2 C6 C5 C4 C3 C2 C1 N1	0.012	0.020 (C7)	

Figure S2 ORTEP view of *mer*-[Fe(L5)₃]²⁺ in the crystal structure of [Fe(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (**I**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and ClO₄⁻ counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Table S7 Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for [Fe(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (**I**).

Bond distances (Å)			
Fe(1)-N(2C)	2.2074(18)	Fe(1)-N(2B)	2.2757(19)
Fe(1)-N(1B)	2.1609(18)	Fe(1)-N(1)	2.1327(18)
Fe(1)-N(1C)	2.1343(18)	Fe(1)-N(2)	2.2427(19)
Bond angles (°)			
N(2C)-Fe(1)-N(2B)	81.33(7)	N(1C)-Fe(1)-N(2)	101.46(7)
N(2C)-Fe(1)-N(2)	178.12(6)	N(1)-Fe(1)-N(2C)	102.85(7)
N(1B)-Fe(1)-N(2C)	99.07(7)	N(1)-Fe(1)-N(1B)	101.92(7)
N(1B)-Fe(1)-N(2B)	75.86(7)	N(1)-Fe(1)-N(1C)	87.22(7)
N(1B)-Fe(1)-N(2)	82.72(7)	N(1)-Fe(1)-N(2B)	175.60(7)
N(1C)-Fe(1)-N(2C)	76.69(7)	N(1)-Fe(1)-N(2)	77.27(7)
N(1C)-Fe(1)-N(1B)	170.64(7)	N(2)-Fe(1)-N(2B)	98.60(7)
N(1C)-Fe(1)-N(2B)	95.15(7)		

Table S8 Selected least-squares planes data for complex for $[\text{Fe}(\text{L5})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**I**).

Least Squares Planes Description	Mean Deviation (Å)	Max. Deviation (Å) and atom	Dihedral Angle (°)
Pyrazine 1 N2 C13 C12 N4 C10 C9	0.017	0.025 (C9A)	40.4
Benzimidazole 1 N1 C8 N3 C6 C5 C4 C3 C2 C1	0.004	0.006 (N3A)	
Pyrazine 2 N2B C13B C12B N4B C10B C9B	0.022	0.033 (C9B)	40.2
Benzimidazole 2 C8B N1B C1B C2B C3B C4B C5B C6B N3B	0.028	0.040 (C6B)	
Pyrazine 3 N2C C13C C12C N4C C10C C9C	0.036	0.054 (C9C)	34.9
Benzimidazole 3 C8C N3C C6C C5C C4C C3C C2C C1C N1C	0.02	0.027 (C8C)	

Figure S3 ORTEP view of $mer\text{-}[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3]^{2+}$ in the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**II**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and ClO_4^- counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Table S9 Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for [Ni(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (II).

Bond distances (Å)			
Ni(1)-N(1A)	2.069(3)	Ni(1)-N(2A)	2.117(3)
Ni(1)-N(1B)	2.070(3)	Ni(1)-N(2B)	2.142(3)
Ni(1)-N(1C)	2.114(3)	Ni(1)-N(2C)	2.162(3)
Bond angles (°)			
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(1B)	86.25(11)	N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	176.17(11)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(1C)	173.50(11)	N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2A)	97.34(10)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(2A)	78.94(10)	N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	81.94(10)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	101.75(10)	N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	78.27(10)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	95.87(11)	N(2A)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	179.18(10)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(1C)	99.76(11)	N(2A)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	82.33(10)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2A)	101.24(10)	N(2B)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	97.14(10)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	79.28(11)		

Table S10 Selected least-squares planes data for complex [Ni(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (II)

Least Squares Planes Description	Mean Deviation (Å)	Max. Deviation (Å) and atom	Dihedral Angle (°)
Benzimidazole 1 N2A C13A C12A N4A C10A C9A	0.04	0.061 (C9A)	33.6
Pyrazine 1 C8A N1A C1A C2A C3A C4A C5A C6A N3A	0.019	0.027 (C3A)	
Benzimidazole 2 C13B C12B N4B C10B C9B N2B	0.022	0.034 (C9B)	38
Pyrazine 2 C8B N1B C1B C2B C3B C4B C5B C6B N3B	0.005	0.008 (C5B)	
Benzimidazole 3 N2C C9C C10C N4C C12C C13C	0.024	0.037 (C9C)	39.7
Pyrazine 3 C8C N1C C1C C2C C3C C4C C5C C6C N3C	0.034	0.053 (C6C)	

Figure S4 ORTEP view of the two different fac - $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3]^{2+}$ cations in the asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**III**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and BF_4^- counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Table S11 Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**III**).

Bond distances (Å)			
Ni(1)-N(1)	2.101(2)	Ni(2)-N(2E)	2.108(2)
Ni(1)-N(1B)	2.067(2)	Ni(2)-N(1F)	2.059(2)
Ni(1)-N(2)	2.1199(19)	Ni(2)-N(2D)	2.147(2)
Ni(1)-N(1C)	2.0756(19)	Ni(2)-N(1D)	2.084(2)
Ni(1)-N(2C)	2.138(2)	Ni(2)-N(1E)	2.094(2)
Ni(1)-N(2B)	2.122(2)	Ni(2)-N(2F)	2.127(2)

Bond angles (°)			
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2)	79.73(8)	N(2E)-Ni(2)-N(2D)	96.02(8)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	83.30(8)	N(2E)-Ni(2)-N(2F)	96.36(9)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	176.06(8)	N(1F)-Ni(2)-N(2E)	86.11(8)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(1)	102.44(8)	N(1F)-Ni(2)-N(2D)	174.08(8)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2)	84.56(8)	N(1F)-Ni(2)-N(1D)	98.99(8)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(1C)	99.30(8)	N(1F)-Ni(2)-N(1E)	102.97(8)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	174.27(8)	N(1F)-Ni(2)-N(2F)	78.28(8)
N(1B)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	78.98(8)	N(1D)-Ni(2)-N(2E)	174.86(8)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	96.78(8)	N(1D)-Ni(2)-N(2D)	78.84(8)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	96.81(8)	N(1D)-Ni(2)-N(1E)	99.74(8)
N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(1)	99.00(8)	N(1D)-Ni(2)-N(2F)	84.19(8)
N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2)	176.13(8)	N(1E)-Ni(2)-N(2E)	79.54(8)
N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	79.42(8)	N(1E)-Ni(2)-N(2D)	82.87(8)
N(1C)-Ni(1)-N(2B)	84.33(8)	N(1E)-Ni(2)-N(2F)	175.57(8)
N(2B)-Ni(1)-N(2C)	95.32(8)	N(2F)-Ni(2)-N(2D)	95.97(8)

Table S12 Selected least-squares planes data for complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**III**).

Unit 1		
Least Squares Planes Description	Max. Deviation (Å)	Dihedral Angle (°)
Benzimidazole 1	0.01	
N1 C8 N3 C6 C5 C4 C3 C2 C1		43.86
Pyrazine 1	0.029	
N2 C13 C12 N4 C10 C9		
Benzimidazole 2	0.009	
C8B N3B N1B C1B C6B C5B C4B C3B C2B		36.1
Pyrazine 2	0.026	
C9B C10B N4B C12B C13B N2B		
Benzimidazole 3	0.008	
C8C N3C C6C C1C N1C C5C C4C C3C C2C		40.8
Pyrazine 3	0.029	
N4C C10C C9C N2C C13C C12C		

Unit 2

Least Squares Planes Description	Max. Deviation (Å)	Dihedral Angle (°)
Benzimidazole 1 C8D N1D C1D C2D C3D C4D C5D C6D N3D	0.009	<u>40.8</u>
Pyrazine 1 C9D N2D C13D C12D N4D C10D	0.032	
Benzimidazole 2 N1E C8E N3E C6E C1E C2E C3E C4E C5E	0.011	38.3
Pyrazine 2 C9E N2E C13E C12E N4E C10E	0.032	
Benzimidazole 3 N1F C1F C2F C3F C4F C5F C6F N3F C8F	0.007	35.52
Pyrazine 3 C9F N2F C13F C12F N4F C10F	0.029	

Figure S5 ORTEP view of $mer-[Zn(L5)_3]^{2+}$ cation in the crystal structure of $[Zn(L5)_3](ClO_4)_2$ (**IV**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and ClO_4^- counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Table S13 Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for [Zn(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (IV).

Bond distances (Å)			
Zn(1)-N(2)	2.1901(18)	Zn(1)-N(1B)	2.0992(18)
Zn(1)-N(1C)	2.1369(17)	Zn(1)-N(2C)	2.3130(19)
Zn(1)-N(1)	2.1081(17)	Zn(1)-N(2B)	2.2554(18)
Bond angles (°)			
N(2)-Zn(1)-N(2C)	81.53(7)	N(1)-Zn(1)-N(2B)	101.22(7)
N(2)-Zn(1)-N(2B)	177.47(7)	N(1B)-Zn(1)-N(2)	104.37(7)
N(1C)-Zn(1)-N(2)	98.46(7)	N(1B)-Zn(1)-N(1C)	102.17(7)
N(1C)-Zn(1)-N(2C)	75.73(7)	N(1B)-Zn(1)-N(1)	88.61(7)
N(1C)-Zn(1)-N(2B)	82.19(7)	N(1B)-Zn(1)-N(2C)	174.03(7)
N(1)-Zn(1)-N(2)	77.70(7)	N(1B)-Zn(1)-N(2B)	77.83(7)
N(1)-Zn(1)-N(1C)	169.18(7)	N(2B)-Zn(1)-N(2C)	96.29(7)
N(1)-Zn(1)-N(2C)	93.62(7)		

Table S14 Selected least-squares planes data for complex [Zn(L5)₃](ClO₄)₂ (IV).

Least Squares Planes Description	Mean Deviation (Å)	Max. Deviation (Å) and atom	Dihedral Angle (°)
Pyrazine 1 N2 C13 C12 N4 C10 C9	0.037	0.056 (C9)	35.2
Benzimidazole 1 C8 N1 C0AA C6 N3 C5 C4 C3 C2	0.019	0.028 (C8)	
Pyrazine 2 N2B C13B C12B N4B C10B C9B	0.018	0.028 (C9B)	<u>40.5</u>
Benzimidazole 2 C8B N1B C1B C2B C3B C4B C5B C6B N3B	0.005	0.009 (C8B)	
Pyrazine 3 C9C C10C N4C C12C C13C N2C	0.02	0.031 (C9C)	41.3
Benzimidazole 3 C8C N3C C6C C5C C4C C3C C2C C1C N1C	0.029	0.042 (C6C)	

Table S15 Crystal data and structure refinement for [Ni(L5)₃](BF₄)₂·1.75CH₃CN (V) and [Zn(L5)₃](BF₄)₂·1.5CH₃CN (VI).

	V	VI
Empirical formula	C _{42.50} H _{41.25} B ₂ F ₈ N _{13.75} Ni	C ₄₂ H _{40.50} B ₂ F ₈ N _{13.50} Zn
Formula Unit	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ B ₂ F ₈ N ₁₂ Ni + (CH ₃ CN) _{1.75}	C ₃₉ H ₃₆ B ₂ F ₈ N ₁₂ Ni + (CH ₃ CN) _{1.5}
Formula weight	976.84	973.35
Temperature	180.15 K	180.01(10) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	1.54184 Å
Crystal system	Trigonal	Trigonal
Space group	<i>P3c1</i>	<i>P3c1</i>
Unit cell dimensions	<i>a</i> = 20.8028(3) Å	<i>a</i> = 21.05979(9) Å
	<i>b</i> = 20.8028(3) Å	<i>b</i> = 21.05979(9) Å
	<i>c</i> = 29.5237(4) Å	<i>c</i> = 29.40349(14) Å
	<i>α</i> = 90°	<i>α</i> = 90°
	<i>β</i> = 90°	<i>β</i> = 90°
	<i>γ</i> = 120°	<i>γ</i> = 120°
Volume	11064.8(3) Å ³	11293.73(11) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	10.00002	10.0002
Density (calculated)	1.466 Mg/m ³	1.431 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.522 mm ⁻¹	1.461 mm ⁻¹
<i>F</i> (000)	5024	4990
Crystal size	0.293 x 0.275 x 0.21 mm ³	0.293 x 0.275 x 0.21 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	2.076 to 28.169°	3.862 to 68.937°
Index ranges	-27 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 26, -27 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 26, -38 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 38	-25 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 25, -25 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 25, -35 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 35
Reflections collected	115787	175735
Independent reflections	16823 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0438]	13967 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0323]
Completeness to theta	(25.242°) 99.90%	(67.684°) 100%
Absorption correction	Gaussian	Gaussian
Max. and min. transmission	1.000 and 0.332	1.000 and 0.670
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data / restraints / parameters	16823 / 156 / 1043	13967 / 93 / 1034
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.031	1.036
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0526, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1295	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0534, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1508
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0815, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1496	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0564, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1558
Extinction coefficient	n/a	n/a
Largest diff. peak and hole	1.679 and -0.687 e.Å ⁻³	1.608 and -0.434 e.Å ⁻³
Absolute structure parameter	0.50(2)	0.12(3)

Figure S6 ORTEP view of the five different fac - $[\text{Ni}(\text{L}5)_3]^{2+}$ cations in the asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L}5)_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 1.75\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (**V**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and BF_4^- counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Figure S7 ORTEP view of the five different fac - $[\text{Zn}(\text{L}5)_3]^{2+}$ cations in the asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of $[\text{Zn}(\text{L}5)_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (**VI**) with partial numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. Hydrogen atoms and BF_4^- counter anions are omitted for clarity.

Figure S8. Optimized superimposition of the molecular structures of **L2** (blue) and **L5** (red) in their respective crystal structures. The nitrogen donor atoms of the α,α' -diimine chelate units are highlighted as spheres to show the anti-conformation.

Figure S9. a) Extended Hückel frontier orbitals computed from gas-phase geometries optimized at the MM2 level and b) experimental electronic absorption spectra for ligands **L2** and **L5** in acetonitrile at 293 K.

Figure S10. Gas-phase energies computed for **L1** and **L2** at the MM2 level using Chem3D as a function of the interplanar angle α [61].

Table S16: Energies of the intrashell d-d transitions, ligand-field strengths (Δ_{oct}) and Racah parameters (B , C) computed with eqns (10)-(13) for $[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**III**) in the solid state and in 0.1 M acetonitrile solution at 298K.

	$[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3](\text{BF}_4)_2$ (solid)	$[\text{Ni}(\text{L5})_3]^{2+}$ (0.1 M CH_3CN)
$\tilde{\nu}({}^3\text{T}_2 \leftarrow {}^3\text{A}_2)/\text{cm}^{-1}$	10672(3) [0.7] ^b	10777(3) [5.8] ^c
$\tilde{\nu}({}^1\text{E} \leftarrow {}^3\text{A}_2)/\text{cm}^{-1}$	12584(6) [0.52] ^b	12470(8) [3.2] ^c
$\tilde{\nu}({}^3\text{T}_1 \leftarrow {}^3\text{A}_2)/\text{cm}^{-1}$	16763(3) [0.97] ^b	17561(2) [10.5] ^c
$\Delta_{\text{oct}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$	10672	10777
B/cm^{-1}	760	983
C/cm^{-1}	3413	2573
Δ_{oct}/B	14.04	10.97
C/B	4.49	2.62
β^a	0.73	0.94

^a Nephelauxetic parameter $\beta = B/B^0$ using $B^0 = 1042 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for free Ni^{2+} ion [77]. ^b Absorbance are given between square brackets. ^c Extinction coefficients in $\text{M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ are given between square brackets.

Figure S11. a) Variation of absorption spectra and b) corresponding variation of observed molar extinctions at different wavelengths recorded for the spectrophotometric titration of **L5** with $\text{Ni}(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2$ (total ligand concentration: $2.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ in acetonitrile, 298 K). c) Evolving factor analysis using four absorbing eigenvectors [48-50], d) re-constructed individual electronic absorption spectra [51-53] and e) associated computed speciation [81].

Figure S12. Ligand speciation computed with HySS2009 for the complex species $[\text{Zn}(\text{L5})_n]^{2+}$ at a total ligand concentration of 1 M and using the stability constants collected in Table 3. [81].

Figure S13. Variable temperature $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{L5})_3]^{2+}$ in CD_3CN (233 K-333 K) with ligand numbering scheme.